

An accurate data-driven physical model for bifacial PV power estimation

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ABSTRACT

Accurate estimation of power plays an important role in designing and monitoring a bifacial PV (BFPV) system. The way to obtain BFPV power by PVlib, as the common simulation approach, is identical to monofacial PV (MFPV), where the bifaciality concept is utilized as a simplifying assumption, and an effective irradiance is employed to consider both front and back radiation together. In addition, during the recent years, a wide range of data-driven approaches, including semi-empirical models, digital twins, and machine learning techniques such as artificial neural networks and ensemble methods, have been explored for BFPV power estimation. While these methods have shown promising accuracy, most of them still rely on rear irradiance measurements, albedo assumptions, or extensive input parameters, which limits their generalizability in real-world BFPV scenarios. Considering the mentioned points, we presented a novel physical data-driven model for estimation of BFPV power output (called the DBPG2 model). The big advantage of DBPG2 model compared to models in the literature is that it does not need rear tilted irradiance (RTI) or albedo and module bifaciality coefficient. The DBPG2 model is trained and tested for a variety of BFPV systems in different parts of the world, with various configurations and albedo conditions. It includes: (1) A fixed-tilt (FT) system at Technical University of Denmark (DTU), (2) A single axis tracking (SAT) system at DTU, (3) A vertically mounted system in Turku, Finland, (4) One row from Bifacial Experimental Single-axis Tracking (BEST) system of National Renewable Energy Lab (NREL) in the Colorado, the USA, and (5 and 6) SAT systems with black and white ground in EURAC Research, Bolzano, Italy. They are called DTU FT, DTU SAT, Turku VER, NREL BEST SAT, EURAC SAT Black Ground, and EURAC SAT White Ground, respectively. According to the results, due to high changes in the albedo over time and small size of the string, the DBPG2 model has a higher error than PVlib for Turku VER (2.47% vs. 1.60%). However, it outperforms PVlib in all other case studies. The normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) for the DBPG2 model and PVlib are: 0.61% and 0.95% (DTU FT), 0.61% and 0.97% (DTU SAT), 1.88% and 3.01% (NREL BEST SAT), 0.77% and 2.07% (EURAC SAT Black Ground), and 1.44% and 3.85% (EURAC SAT White Ground). The findings show a more significant improvement of the DBPG2 model in comparison to PVlib for high albedo and single axis tracker, which is usually the preferred working condition of BFPV systems.

Nomenclature

Symbols

<i>RTI</i>	Rear tilted irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>NMBE</i>	Normalized mean bias error
<i>NMAE</i>	Normalized mean absolute error
<i>T</i>	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
<i>PR</i>	Performance ratio, defined as the ratio of the produced power, normalized by the nominal (STC) power, to the irradiance input, normalized by the STC reference value.
<i>G</i>	Irradiance (W/m^2)

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<i>P</i>	Power (W)
<i>K_{CS}</i>	Clearness index
<i>AOI</i>	Angle of incidence (deg)
<i>DBPG</i>	Dynamic bifacial power gain
<i>EL</i>	Elevation angle (deg)
<i>AZ</i>	Azimuth angle (deg)
<i>G_{TI}</i>	Global (front) tilted irradiance (W/m^2)
<i>t</i>	Time (s or min or hr)
<i>period</i>	The investigated period
<i>Y</i>	Yield ($kWh/kW_{P,Front}^{BF}$)

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SS	Skill (selection) score
<i>a</i>	Coefficients of the DBPG2 model polynomials
NRMSE	Normalized root mean square error
Greek symbols	
γ	The temperature coefficient of maximum power (%/°C)
φ	Bifaciality
Subscripts	
<i>amb</i>	Ambient
<i>p</i>	Peak
<i>min</i>	The minimum
<i>temp corr</i>	Temperature corrected
<i>E</i>	Effective
<i>n</i>	The nominal condition
<i>rear</i>	Rear side
Superscripts	
<i>PVlib</i>	PVlib
<i>model</i>	Model
<i>BF</i>	Bifacial PV
<i>MF</i>	Monofacial PV
<i>front</i>	Front side
<i>est</i>	Estimated
<i>exp</i>	Experimental
Abbreviations	
NOCT	Nominal operating cell temperature
ANN	Artificial neural network
MPP	Maximum power point
FT	Fixed-tilt
IEA	The International Energy Agency
SAT	Single-axis tracking
SAPM	Sandia array performance model
MFPV	Monofacial PV
BFPV	Bifacial PV
PV	Photovoltaic
PLR	Performance Loss Rate
VER	Vertically mounted
PERC	Passivated emitter and rear contact technology
HJT	Heterojunction technology
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
NREL BEST	The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Bifacial Experimental Single-axis Tracking system
NMOT	Nominal module operating temperature
STC	The standard test condition
DBPG1 <i>model</i>	The first DBPG model, which requires RTI.
DBPG2 <i>model</i>	The second DBPG model, which eliminates the need for RTI or albedo.

1. Introduction

There is an increasing interest in the utilization of the bifacial photovoltaic (BFPV) technologies to overcome the current energy crises all around the world [1–3]. The 14th Global Roadmap on PV Technologies [4] estimated that the current shares of monofacial photovoltaic (MFPV) and BFPV in the world market are ~65 % and ~35 %, respectively. In 2027, BFPV is forecasted to take the lead with a contribution of ~55 %. Three years later, i.e., in 2030, BFPV share will be ~60 %.

For a BFPV system accurate estimation of power is of great importance in several areas, including the feasibility assessment, size determination, techno-economic evaluation, performance optimization, fault detection, and forecasting provision [5–7]. A widely-used way to estimate power is application of PVlib [8]. PVlib represents a key reference framework in PV power estimation, containing the standard thermal and electrical models capable of simulating both MFPV and BFPV systems performance under diverse conditions. Several studies have employed PVlib for BFPV systems, including [9,10] focusing on assessing the feasibility, [11,12] regarding the evaluation from a techno-economic point of view, [13,14] aiming at optimizing the performance, [15,16] addressing fault detection, and [17,18] providing forecast. In PVlib, the same estimation model as MFPV is used for BFPV power, but effective irradiance (G_E) is fed as input.

In addition to PVlib, BFPV power estimation could be done by means of other approaches presented by researchers in the literature. In some of the research works, the approach has been able to estimate current and voltage separately. For instance, Bouchakour et al. [19,20] provided semi-empirical equations to determine voltage and current of a BFPV. There were two coefficients for each of the current and voltage equation. The input variables of the current equation were the module specifications, temperature and G_E . The input variables of the voltage equation were the ones used for the current equation in addition to thermal voltage and number of cells in series. The values estimated by the proposed semi-empirical approach were compared to the ones obtained from the analytical approach of Ortiz Rivera et al. [21]. The results showed that the accuracy of both analytical approach of [21] and the semi-empirical model declined when irradiance decreased. Moreover, the analytical approach of [21] was found more accurate than the semi-empirical one for the investigated case-study, which was a fixed-tilted (FT) system in Terrassa, Spain. The average daily errors for the semi-empirical model were 1.55% and 5.28%, and for the analytical approach of [21], they were 0.51% and 2.82%, respectively.

In another study, a digital twin was proposed by Yuan et al. [22] to determine voltage and current of a BFPV unit. The digital twin worked based on the two-diode equivalent circuit with a boosted parameter estimation using four-state Jaya evolutionary algorithm. The input variables of the digital twin included a number of variables, including G_E , temperature, and module characteristics. Accuracy assessment using the recorded data for a stand-alone module with FT configuration indicated a good agreement between the simulation and experiment. A RMSE range of ~2% to 6.25% was observed. Furthermore, a comparative study was done by Mannino et al. [23] to compare some semi-empirical equations for voltage and current estimation of a BFPV plant. Their comparison covered Sandia Array Performance Model (SAPM) [24], as well as the approaches provided by Cristaldi et al. [25] and Faifer et al. [26] (Cristaldi- Faifer method). The investigation was carried out for a BFPV unit with FT configuration in Catania, Italy, while models' parameters were estimated based on the given input variables. According to the results, SAPM model had RMSE of about 0.20–0.49 A for maximum power point (MPP) current. It reached around 0.27–0.53 A using the Cristaldi- Faifer method. A high dependence of the results on the fitting method was observed.

In another study, Sahu et al. [27] developed a single-diode electrical model for bifacial PV modules, where each circuit parameter was expressed as a function of front and rear side values. A correction factor was introduced to account for photocurrent mismatch between the two sides. Experimental validation showed that the model significantly reduced errors in I–V curve and MPP power estimation compared to benchmark models. Error values of ~12% and ~7% were observed before and after using the correction factor.

Zhang et al. [28] proposed a novel semi-empirical model to modify the given effective irradiance to the single-diode model. The modification was based on the concept of dynamic bifaciality, which accounts for both irradiance intensity and rear-side non-uniformity. Using I–V curve measurements under varying irradiance, they determined the real bifaciality. Then, a 3D optical-electrical model ran and a correction factor was proposed to relate the theoretical and real values. The correction factor was linked to non-uniformity and other input variables like height, slope, and the average received irradiance through a polynomial fit, enabling fast calculation of dynamic bifaciality. This value replaced the static (constant) bifaciality in power estimation by the single-diode model, significantly improving accuracy—reducing the mean absolute error from 6.07% to 1.14% and from 8.10% to 1.40% at non-uniformity levels of 14.6% and 23.2%, respectively.

Li et al. [29] presented a physics-based methodology named PV-Pro, which dynamically updated a single-diode equivalent circuit model using recent production and weather data to reflect the current degradation status of field PV systems. Unlike conventional physical models that relied on fixed datasheet parameters or costly I–V characterization,

PV-Pro iteratively extracted parameters (photocurrent, series/shunt resistance, diode factor) by minimizing the error between measured and simulated current/voltage. Validation was performed on synthetic datasets and four real mono-crystalline MFPV field systems, where PV-Pro was compared with smart-persistence, nominal models, and several machine-learning approaches. Using the measured module temperature and plane-of-array irradiance, PV-Pro achieved an average normalized MAE of 1.4%, reducing error by 17.6% compared to the best examined alternative (Kernel Ridge machine-learning model). It consistently showed robustness across seasons and varying degradation severities, making it effective for both aged and newly installed PV systems.

Ahmed et al. [30] developed a physics-based modeling method for BFPV modules by modifying standard single-diode and double-diode models. They introduced an extra parameter to adapt series resistance, capturing the nonlinear behavior of BFPV operation under combined front- and rear-side irradiance. To determine parameters, they applied a two-stage optimization. First, monofacial data at 1000 W/m^2 front irradiance were used to extract conventional parameters, then bifacial data refined the added resistance. Validation employed I–V curves of a commercial BFPV module, comparing estimated and datasheet data, and error metrics such as RMSE, MAE, and coefficient of determination. Results showed RMSE reductions (0.0538 vs. 0.4519) and excellent fits, proving the method's accuracy.

Becerra et al. [31] developed and assessed a physics-based framework to analyze the electrical models of BFPV modules using real laboratory data. Various single- and double-diode formulations, including a parallel single-diode approach, were implemented to simulate IV curves, with parameters obtained from manufacturer data and corrected by measured irradiance and temperature. Validation was performed indoors under controlled conditions using a solar simulator, applying both single-sided and double-sided illumination tests on PERC+, HJT, and n-PERT modules. Modelled IV curves were compared with experimental ones, and errors were calculated across current, voltage, and power regions. Results showed shadowing from frames and junction boxes as key error sources, while single-diode model provided by Gu et al. [32] yielded the best agreement, with the current errors approaching around 20%. This work focused entirely on bifacial PV systems.

Instead of separate estimation of current and voltage, in another group of the studies, power has been obtained directly. An artificial neural network (ANN) was provided in Ref. [33] which was able to estimate electricity production of a BFPV system with FT configuration on a rooftop of a building in Sharjah, the UAE, as a function of several parameters, including weather and system parameters (PVSyst-generated data). The input data was supplied from PVSyst simulation. Their results demonstrated that increasing the albedo from 0.2 to 0.8 led to a rise in the mean square error from 0.14 to 0.17 kW, indicating a reduction in the model accuracy under higher ground reflectance conditions. Additionally, in study of Yunqiao and Yan [34], BFPV power modeling was done using bidirectional gated recurrent unit network considering a FT system in Jiuquan, China. A bifacial irradiance correction factor was given as the input variable based on the criteria such as cleanliness of module and ground reflectance. A good accuracy was seen while quantifying the reflection and module cleanliness were detected as two serious challenges. RMSE were evaluated for different sample clear-sky, cloudy, snowy, and complex days, showing a range between 0.316 and 2.284 MW. May et al. [35] also compared the ability of random forest and AdaBoost to estimate power output of different PV technologies, including BFPV, mounted on a FT track in Pretoria, South Africa. The input variables were some module specifications, wind speed, and plane of array irradiance, as well as module and ambient temperatures. High accuracy of RF for all the technologies had been observed based on the conducted analysis. The RMSE for AdaBoost were between 13.7 W and 58.9 W for different investigated modules. It had been reached the range of 3.2 W–9.4 W by applying RF.

As the summation of power in a specific period of time, some

investigations introduced ways to estimate the yield directly. A linear function had been given by Castillo-Aguilella and Hauser [36] to obtain the bifacial energy gain. Their proposed function took module height, ground albedo, and tilt angle as its input parameters. Accuracy evaluation was carried out for a number of FT BFPV systems with different tilt angles, located in New York and Arizona, the USA. A satisfactory level of error was seen. A standard deviation of 3.5% had been reported considering the whole cases. Furthermore, Ghenai et al. [37] employed the response surface methodology to simulate the performance of a BFPV unit. Their training data came from PVSyst simulation. They considered module height, albedo, and tilt angle as the input variables and found quadratic polynomials to determine the impact on bifacial energy gain and energy production during a year. The coefficient of determination for the proposed approach was 0.9983 for the training data. A similar study was also done by Radwan et al. [38] for a BFPV system in Sharjah, UAE. In that study, in addition to the height, albedo, and tilt angle, module spacing had been added to the input variables. The module height had been identified as the variable with the lowest impact on both annual energy and bifacial energy gain among the four. Comparing the simulated and real data for a year showed a range between 1.6% and 23.3% for the monthly error.

In another work, Rodriguez-Pastor et al. [39] modelled a BFPV system in agriculture application by incorporating the electrical modeling, heat transfer calculations, and view factor method. Having developed and validated their model, some plots were drawn to see the correlation between some performance indicators. The plots included the estimated energy vs. estimated front irradiance and estimated energy vs. rear irradiance. The values of 92.8% and 67.5% for the coefficient of determination were reported, respectively. Moreover, Alam et al. [40,41] employed correlation to find empirical models for a BFPV unit with FT configuration in the UK. The empirical models were established for three sets of relationships: Rear irradiance gain and bifacial energy gain, G_E and power output, and total clearness index and rear irradiance gain. The RMSE values for the empirical models for the first two indicated pairs were 2.9% and 5 W. The third correlation had been developed for four different ground covers, resulting in an RMSE between 1% and 4%.

In addition, a physical data-driven model to estimate power of a BFPV system was proposed by the authors of this paper in Ref. [42]. The modeling approach introduced the DBPG concept to describe the rear side production. RTI must be available to run the model as it is multiplied by a coefficient to obtain DBPG. The coefficient can be considered as the rear-side performance ratio, and it was found using the historical data. Results demonstrated that the model (called DBPG1) outperformed PVlib in both power and yield estimation (NRMSE of 1.14% vs. 2.99% for the low albedo case, and 2.02% vs. 4.59% for the high albedo case).

Most of the existing models in the literature, including PVlib and those introduced here, need RTI or albedo for power estimation. However, RTI or albedo data are not available for many cases in reality. Even if they are available from the experimental data, measurement usually includes the value for only one or two points. This means not considering the edge effect that reduces the power estimation accuracy. Using simulation tools, as another alternative, often imposes high computational cost, time, and difficulty, while their accuracy drops by increasing the albedo. For these reasons, we upgraded our DBPG1 model [42] to a new model (called DBPG2) to provide an accurate BFPV power estimation model which does not need any RTI or albedo input which represents the major novelty compared to the previous literature. The proposed model is data-driven and works in a way that it could also capture the edge effect as a very important phenomenon in a BFPV system. The model development and input parameters selection are done in a way that it reflects a meaningful description of the process, which means the proposed model is a physical model, as well.

The model is trained and tested for six different BFPV systems. They include fixed tilt (FT) and single axis tracking (SAT) installations, as well as the vertical configuration (VER), located in various parts of the world with diverse surface reflectance (albedo) conditions. This variety

ensures a comprehensive validation of the model performance under real-world scenarios. The modeling results are compared with PVlib simulation, as the widely-adopted approach for this purpose. For PVlib, different pairs of electrical and thermal models are examined to find the most accurate of them for each case, which is the one compared with our data-driven physical model.

The paper has been organized in 5 sections: section 1 is the introduction, which has been ended here. Section 2 describes the methodology, section 3 introduces the investigated case studies, and section 4 discusses and analyzes the results. Finally, the summary and conclusion are given in section 5.

2. Methodology

The methodology applied in this work has been discussed here. First, in section 2.1, the core conceptual foundation of the DBPG modeling approach is established. After that, in section 2.2, the details of the first DBPG model, referred to as DBPG1 and originally presented in the authors' previous work [42], are presented. The DBPG1 model requires RTI. Section 2.3 then presents the new DBPG model. It is called the second DBPG (the DBPG2) model, which eliminates the need for RTI or albedo. Next, section 2.4 describes the PVlib approach. This widely used method serves as the reference for benchmarking and comparative purposes. Finally, in section 2.5, the procedure adopted for data filtering is explained.

2.1. Dynamic bifacial power gain (DBPG) model principles

In our Dynamic Bifacial Power Gain (DBPG) modelling approach, BFPV power (P^{BF}) is considered in the form of:

$$P^{BF} = P^{MF} + P_n^{BF,front} DBPG \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) is schematically shown in Fig. 1, as well.

In Eq. (1), $P_n^{BF,front}$ indicates the nominal power of the front side of BFPV, and P^{MF} denotes power of MFPV at the same global tilted irradiance (G_{TI}) and ambient temperature (T_{amb}) as BFPV. Dynamic Bifacial Power Gain (DBPG) is also defined as:

$$DBPG = \frac{P^{BF} - P^{MF}}{P_n^{BF,front}} \quad (2)$$

DBPG is different from the bifaciality coefficient [43].

An installed BFPV plant usually consists of only bifacial modules and there is no MFPV on-site with the same front side specifications (like the investigated case-studies). Consequently, simulation is utilized to obtain MFPV power, and using the proposed model, BFPV power is estimated

by:

$$P_{est}^{BF,DBPG\ model} = P_{est}^{MF}(G_{TI}, T_{amb}) + P_n^{BF,front} DBPG_{est}^{DBPG\ model} \quad (3)$$

Where $P_{est}^{MF}(G_{TI}, T_{amb})$ is the estimated MFPV power. It could be determined through any MFPV modelling approach (In this work, PVlib is used). $DBPG_{est}^{DBPG\ model}$ is also the dynamic bifacial power gain of Eq. (1) obtained from the modelling.

2.2. DBPG1 model

The performance ratio (PR) for a PV system describes the real performance compared to a reference case (e.g., Standard Test Condition (STC)). PR can be evaluated either on the basis of instantaneous power production or over a given period with the cumulative sum of power values, i.e., the energy yield [1,44,45]. In practice, the energy yield-based calculation is more common [46]. However, since the objective of the DBPG1 model is to determine backside power production as an instantaneous output rather than the yield as an integrated quantity, its development has been carried out by adopting the PR definition based on the power value.

In this definition, PR is expressed as the ratio of the produced power, normalized by the nominal (STC) power, to the irradiance input, normalized by the STC reference value:

$$PR = \frac{\frac{P}{G}}{\frac{P_{STC}}{G_{STC}}} \quad (4)$$

Using the definition of Eq. (4), the performance ratio of the rear side (PR_{rear}) is:

$$PR_{rear} = \frac{\frac{P_{rear}}{P_{STC}}}{\frac{G_{rear}}{G_{STC}}} \quad (5)$$

DBPG is the produced power by the rear side of modules in a BFPV system, normalized by the nominal (STC) power (Eq. (2)). Therefore, the numerator of fraction in Eq. (5) is DBPG. The irradiance input for the rear side is RTI. The corresponding irradiance input to produce the nominal power (STC value) is also 1000 W/m². Therefore:

$$PR_{rear} = \frac{DBPG}{\frac{RTI}{1000}} \quad (6)$$

Taking Eq. (6) into consideration, in Ref. [42], the authors proposed a first data driven approach (called DBPG1 model) to estimate the DBPG from historical rear-tilted irradiance (RTI) data:

Fig. 1. The graphical representation of the proposed approach [42].

$$DBPG_{est}^{DBPG1\ model} = PR_{rear} \times \left(\frac{RTI}{1000} \right) \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) establishes a linear relationship between RTI and $DBPG$, with the slope representing the performance ratio of the rear side. $DBPG$ and $\frac{RTI}{1000}$ are both dimensionless. Therefore, PR_{rear} does not also have a unit, obtained as an empirical coefficient from linear regression using the historical training data. More details could be found in Ref. [42].

2.3. DBPG2 model

The DBPG1 model provides a straightforward linear relationship but shares a key limitation with most of the existing models in the literature: its need for RTI . As discussed, RTI data might be unavailable for a BFPV system. Even when available, measurement is usually performed at a single point, failing to capture crucial spatial effects like the edge effect or non-uniform albedo across the field. Furthermore, models relying on simulated RTI often incur high computational costs and may lose accuracy under high albedo conditions. To overcome these issues, this work introduces the DBPG2 model, with the central objective of achieving full independence from RTI and albedo inputs, thus overcoming the aforementioned limitations.

The DBPG2 model directly estimates $DBPG$ from readily available meteorological and sun-position-related parameters instead of relying on rear-side irradiance measurements. By doing so, the model inherently captures system-specific phenomena, including irradiance non-uniformity, module soiling, and degradation, which have been already embedded in the historical power data used for training. This dual nature makes the model both data-driven, as it leverages observed behavior, and physical, as it encodes variables that are meaningful in the context of BFPV operation.

$DBPG$ is estimated by the DBPG2 model with the polynomial function that considers the physical relation between RTI and selected variables. In contrast to black-box approaches (e.g., neural networks or ensemble methods), it offers superior interpretability, avoids unphysical extrapolations, requires less data for robust training, and is less prone to overfitting. Its relatively simple formulation also facilitates practical implementation. At the same time, compared to overly simple empirical models (e.g., purely linear formulations or low-order correlations), the polynomial structure provides the necessary flexibility to represent fundamental non-linear behaviors (such as the saturation effect of clear-sky irradiance on rear-side gain) and interaction effects among physical variables (for example, the intensified influence of albedo at low solar elevation angles).

For FT, the polynomial is a function of clearness index (K_{CS}), as a representative of solar radiation, and cosine of angle of incidence ($\cos(AOI)$) as a factor reflecting the relative position of BFPV to the sun. For SAT, azimuth and elevation angles (AZ and EL) should be also added to the effective parameters. Therefore:

$$DBPG_{est}^{DBPG2\ model} = \begin{cases} g_{FT}(\cos(AOI), K_{CS}) & \text{Fixed-tilt (FT)} \\ g_{SAT}(\cos(AOI), K_{CS}, AZ, EL) & \text{Single-axis tracking (SAT)} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The complete forms of the equations are introduced in section 4.2 in addition to the coefficients for each case-study. The coefficients of the polynomials are not predefined; rather, they are rigorously estimated from historical system data through ordinary least squares regression. This calibration step aligns the model with filtered, high-quality measurements, thereby embedding site-specific operational behavior—such as the combined influence of irradiance non-uniformity, soiling, and degradation—directly into the parameters. This constitutes the essence of the data-driven approach: while the polynomial structure is grounded in physical reasoning, its parameters are fully learned from, and subsequently validated against, actual system performance.

2.4. PVlib power estimation approach

Since PVlib is a widely used tool for simulating the power output of not only MFPV, but also BFPV systems, the estimation ability of the DBPG2 model is compared to PVlib. The approach of PVlib for determination of BFPV power is to use the monofacial estimation model but inputting the effective irradiance G_E [8]:

$$P_{est}^{BF, PVlib} = P_{est}^{MF, PVlib}(G_E, T_{amb}) \quad (9)$$

Where:

$$G_E = GTI + \varphi RTI \quad (10)$$

In which, φ is the bifaciality coefficient.

2.5. Data filtering

The training and test of the DBPG2 model were done using filtered daylight data. A statistical filter is applied to remove outliers. It trims the tails of the distribution of the temperature-corrected performance ratio ($PR_{temp\ corr}$):

$$PR_{temp\ corr} = \frac{\frac{p^{BF}}{p^{BF, front}}}{\left(1 + \gamma(T_{PV} - 25)\right) \left(\frac{GTI}{1000} + \varphi \frac{RTI}{1000}\right)} \quad (11)$$

In which, T_{PV} is the temperature of PV cells in degrees Celsius. Additionally, γ denotes the temperature coefficient of the maximum power.

The filtered outliers might come from different reasons, such as the presence of near shading and the incorrect acquisition of some measurements.

3. Case-studies

The DBPG2 model is developed for the estimation of the power output of six BFPV systems. They are shown in Fig. 2. The most important information about the considered BFPV systems is reported in Table 1. The assigned name for each case in Table 1 starts with the location and is followed by the configuration. If two cases have the same location and configuration, a third element is added to the name to distinguish them. It happens for EURAC SAT, where the ground color is used as the third element of the name to differentiate between cases.

As seen in Table 1, the case-studies are located at different parts of the world (Finland, Denmark, the USA, and Italy). They cover various mounting configurations, including FT, SAT, and vertically mounted (VER). In terms of layout, the system arrangements range from a single row with a small number of PV modules (1×4 in Turku VER) to multiple rows with a higher number of PV modules per row (4×22 in DTU FT and DTU SAT). Moreover, the ground coverage during the year is different from a case to another one (The detailed information is available in the references for each case). Various PV technologies are also utilized in the systems, including Passivated emitter and rear contact (PERC) and Heterojunction technology (HJT). Such diversity ensures the model applicability across different scales and deployment conditions.

SAT could be implemented using various strategies. The simplest SAT approach is astronomical algorithm. This is an unconstrained minimization of AOI, ideally aligning the modules surface perpendicular to the incoming irradiance. The astronomical algorithm for SAT adjusts the tilt angle based on solar angles, which could be derived from theoretical calculations with location and time as inputs. However, in large-scale systems this approach might lead to inter-row shading, particularly at low solar elevations. To overcome this, backtracking SAT algorithms could be employed, in which the tilt angle is adjusted to minimize shading losses even at the cost of a slightly higher AOI compared to the astronomical tracking. Backtracking is employed in all four investigated BFPV SAT systems.

Fig. 2. The investigated cases; (a) DTU FT [47]; (b) DTU SAT [47]; (c) Turku VER [48]; (d) NREL BEST SAT [49]; (e) EURAC SAT Black Ground; (f) EURAC SAT White Ground [42].

Table 1

Site information, mounting details, and PV module characteristics for the investigated case-studies.

Parameter	Value/Condition					
Name	DTU FT	DTU SAT	Turku VER	NREL BEST SAT	EURAC SAT Black Ground	EURAC SAT White Ground
Location	Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Roskilde, Denmark	Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Roskilde, Denmark	Turku University of Applied Sciences, Finland	NREL South Table Mountain campus, Golden, Colorado, USA	EURAC Research, Bolzano, Italy	EURAC Research, Bolzano, Italy
Latitude	55.7 °N	55.7 °N	60.4 °N	39.7 °N	46.5 °N	46.5 °N
Longitude	12.1 °E	12.1 °E	22.3 °E	105.1 °W	11.3 °E	11.3 °E
Configuration	FT	SAT	FT (vertically mounted)	SAT	SAT	SAT
Number of PV (rows × PV per row)	4 × 22	4 × 22	1 × 4	1 × 20 ^a	2 × 12	2 × 12
Surface azimuth	180°	90°	90° (Sun on the front) 270° (Sun on the back)	96°	108°	108°
Axis tilt	0°	0	0°	0°	0°	0°
Range for tilt change	Always 25°	±60°	Always 90°	±60°	±55°	±55°
BFPV technology	PERC	PERC	HJT	PERC	HJT	HJT
Nominal front capacity of the used modules ($P_n^{BF,Front}$)	295 W	295 W	295 W	354 W	374 W	374 W
Average bifaciality (φ)	0.67	0.67	0.902	0.694	0.903	0.903
The temperature coefficient of maximum power (γ)	-0.39 %/°C	-0.39 %/°C	-0.4139 %/°C	-0.40 %/°C	-0.250 %/°C	-0.250 %/°C
References for more information	[47,50]	[47,50]	[48,51]	[49,52,53]	[42]	[42]

^a There are 20 modules in the string, but the reported power data refers to the output of 19 modules. The remaining module was connected to a separate data acquisition system with different variables, as it was used for other measurements.

There is also non-uniform distribution of RTI in all the six investigated cases. One reason is that the ground surface materials and their reflectance are not homogeneous within each site. An example is the presence of white gaps in dark surfaces, such as tiled or patterned pavements. Another source of RTI non-uniformity is the reflection from surrounding objects, which can vary depending on the type and position of nearby structures. Moreover, discontinuities such as transparent areas surrounding dark PV cells in a module also one more cause of RTI non-uniformity. As discussed later, the DBPG2 model is able to capture the

non-uniformity of RTI. Such non-uniformity leads to mismatch between cells and rows and reduces the overall energy yield.

4. Results and discussion

The results of this work are presented in this part, in five sections. Initially, in section 4.1, among the different pairs of the available electrical and thermal models in PVLlib, the best-performing one is chosen for each case to be the representative of PVLlib in comparison with the

DBPG2 model. Then, the equations introduced by the DBPG2 model are given in section 4.2 for the investigated BFPV systems. This section is followed by presenting the scatter plots for PVlib and the DBPG2 model for each case to compare accuracy of the models. After that, section 4.3 comes with evaluating the accuracy of PVlib and the DBPG2 model in terms of monthly and total yield estimation. Next, in section 4.4, different approaches for training and testing the DBPG2 model are compared. The compared approaches are: (1) The random selection, used as the default approach to obtain the results in sections 4.1 to 4.3, (2) The annual selection, and (3) Moving window method. Finally, section 4.5 answers the question of which model—DBPG1, DBPG2, or PVlib—achieves the highest accuracy for each case.

It is worth mentioning that the results reported in sections 4.2 to 4.4 were presented with the purpose of evaluating the DBPG2 model in comparison with PVlib. Similar analyses to those shown in these sections for the DBPG2 model have already been provided for the DBPG1 model in Ref. [42] where it was originally introduced. Considering this, and in order to maintain the focus on the performance of the DBPG2 model proposed in the present work, as well as to avoid overcrowding of figures, analyses, and overall length of the manuscript, the comparisons in sections 4.2 to 4.4 were limited to the DBPG2 model and PVlib.

4.1. The best-performing thermal and electrical models pairs in PVlib

PVlib provides the possibility to use different thermal and electrical models to simulate the performance of a PV system. Thermal models are employed to estimate the cell temperature under real operating conditions, while electrical models utilize the derived temperature from thermal modeling alongside irradiance data to compute the expected power output. In this work, the electrical and thermal models combination with the highest accuracy is identified for each of the investigated case-studies. For this purpose, for each pair of electrical and thermal models, the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) between the measured and simulated power outputs is determined. The value is then utilized to determine skill score (SS) from Eq. (12):

$$SS_{ij}(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{NRMSE_{ij}}{NRMSE_{min}} \right) \times 100 \tag{12}$$

In which, SS_{ij} and $NRMSE_{ij}$ are the skill score and NRMSE for the pair of i^{th} thermal and j^{th} electrical models, respectively. $NRMSE_{min}$ is also the lowest NRMSE among all the pairs.

For better illustration of the evaluation results, a colorful selection matrix has been created using SS_{ij} values for each case. Fig. 3a–e present the selection matrices of different cases. The reported values are in percent. In these matrices, the horizontal axis shows the applied electrical models, while the vertical axis represents the employed thermal models. The presentation is based on a green–yellow–red color scale, where the most favorable value has been highlighted in the deepest green and the least favorable in the deepest red, with intermediate values represented by gradual transitions through shades of yellow.

The selection matrices in Fig. 3a–e have indicated that for all the cases except for DTU SAT, the best-performing pair utilizes the Ross (also called the Nominal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT)) model [54] for the thermal side. Even for DTU SAT, although the Ross model is not the used thermal model in the top performer pair, it remains part of the second most accurate combination. The high accuracy of the Ross model is likely because NOCT of module, as the only adjustment parameter, is directly provided by the manufacturer in the module datasheet. However, the adjustment parameters required by other models are generally not listed in the datasheet and therefore, have to be assumed or estimated.

The thermal model employed in the best-performing pair in DTU SAT is Sandia Array Performance Model (SAPM) [55]. For other cases, and if we consider the same electrical model to be combined, the error of SAPM thermal model is more than NOCT and less than the others. This is probably because the SAPM thermal model explicitly accounts for modules with a “glass-glass” construction, which is typical for many BFPV modules. In a glass-glass construction, both the front and rear sides are encapsulated with glass, leading to different heat transfer characteristics compared to conventional glass-backsheet modules. Nonetheless, the adjusting parameters for the other thermal models like Faiman

Fig. 3. The colorful selection matrices for the investigated cases to find the best pair of electrical and thermal models in PVlib; (a) DTU FT; (b) DTU SAT; (c) Turku VER; (d) NREL BEST SAT; (e) EURAC SAT Black Ground; (f) EURAC SAT White Ground. The values in the matrices are expressed in percent.

(known as the Nominal Module Operating Temperature (NMOT)) [56], are typically not reported in datasheets and must be assumed or estimated (usually the same as MFPV), which may reduce their accuracy.

Based on Fig. 3a–e, the employed electrical model in the best-performing pair for four cases is the SAPM electrical model [55]. The cases are DTU FT, DTU SAT, Turku VER, and NREL BEST SAT. The commercial BFPV modules are employed for all these four cases and PVlib database contains most of the commercial BFPV modules. Therefore, the possible reason is that we have the adjusting parameters of the SAPM electrical model for those modules (or very similar ones). When those parameters are available, SAPM works very well. However, the custom-made modules are utilized in EURAC SAT (Both black and white ground). The adjustable parameters required for SAPM are not available in this case, whereas those needed for PVWatts are. This could be the reason for higher accuracy of PVWatts for EURAC SAT cases.

4.2. Power estimation ability of the DBPG2 model compared to PVlib

In order to develop the DBPG2 model, 70% of the filtered data has been employed for training, while 30% is kept for test (randomly chosen). Tables 2 and 3 summarize the training data characteristics for the FT and SAT cases, respectively. In Table 2, for Turku VER, as a FT system, two separate columns are presented because, depending on the solar position, the front side (with higher nominal efficiency) sees the sun during part of the day, while during the rest, the back side does. Consequently, the modeling is performed separately for each condition.

The training part is used to find the polynomial coefficients to determine DBPG from Eq. (8). The polynomial model includes second-order terms for each variable, as well as pairwise interaction terms, in addition to an intercept, formulated as Eq. (13) for FT and Eq. (14) for SAT:

$$(DBPG_{est}^{DBPG2\ model})_{FT} = a_0 + a_1 \cos(AOI) + a_2 K_{CS} + a_{12} \cos(AOI)K_{CS} + a_{11} (\cos(AOI))^2 + a_{22} K_{CS}^2 \tag{13}$$

$$(DBPG_{est}^{DBPG2\ model})_{SAT} = a_0 + a_1 \cos(AOI) + a_2 K_{CS} + a_3 AZ + a_4 EL + a_{12} (AOI)K_{CS} + a_{13} \cos(AOI)AZ + a_{14} \cos(AOI)EL + a_{23} K_{CS}AZ + a_{24} K_{CS}EL + a_{34}AZEL + a_{11} (\cos(AOI))^2 + a_{22} K_{CS}^2 + a_{33}AZ^2 + a_{44}EL^2 \tag{14}$$

In Eqs. (13) and (14), the units for AOI, AZ, and EL are all degrees. K_{CS} is dimensionless.

Table 2
Characteristics of the training data for FT cases.

Parameter	Unit	Description	DTU FT	Turku VER (Sun on the front)	Turku VER (Sun on the back)
Number of training data	–	Value	207	16987	13663
Temporal coverage	–	Start End	Feb 2020 Mar 2020	Jan 2018 Jul 2021	Jan 2018 July 2021
Variation range of $\cos(AOI)$	–	Min Max	0.0856 0.8923	5.3842e-06 0.9995	2.5525e-05 0.9992
Variation range of K_{CS}	–	Min Max	0.0540 1.4000	0.0074 1.4000	0.0075 1.4000
Variation range of DBPG	–	Min Max	3.9380e-04 0.0438	4.1058e-05 0.3239	1.6442e-05 0.3660

The coefficients values for FT cases are introduced in Table 4. In this table, there are two columns for Turku VER, in which the modules were installed in the vertical position. The reason is, as also indicated earlier, based on the solar position, in one part of the day the front (the side with higher nominal efficiency) sees the sun, while in another part, the back (the side with lower nominal efficiency) does. Therefore, the modeling must be done separately for each condition.

Similarly, Table 5 gives the coefficients values for SAT cases.

It is important to note that the reported coefficients in Table 4 for Eq. (13) and Table 5 for Eq. (14) are valid for the whole period in each case. This means that the fitted polynomials possess generalizability across different seasons of the year. A separate functional form is not required on a daily basis, since the selected input variables capture the variations in irradiance and solar geometry. Therefore, a single set of coefficients is sufficient to describe the performance of each system consistently throughout the entire investigated period, ensuring that the DBPG2 model provides both robustness under diverse seasonal conditions and simplicity in its practical application.

Figs. 4 and 5 present the scatter plots (experimental vs. modelled) for PVlib and the DBPG2 model for all the six cases. Fig. 4 shows the results for the FT cases, while Fig. 5 presents those for the SAT ones.

Fig. 4a shows that, in the DTU FT case, PVlib has an NRMSE of 0.95% and an NMBE of 0.20%. The RTI data used to calculate power by PVlib came from the measurement by a pyranometer, which had been installed at a point close to the center of the string. However, in reality, there is a spatial distribution for RTI throughout the string. The modules closer to the edge receives more and the ones closer to the center receives less RTI. This is known as the “edge effect”, which PVlib is not able to account for. Another issue about PVlib is it does not consider some operating issues such degradation and soiling. On the other hand, the DBPG2 model was trained using the measured power data directly, in which such effects been accounted. Therefore, both NRMSE and NMBE have been improved by applying the DBPG2 model, for which the values of 0.61% and 0.001% are seen, respectively (Fig. 4b). It indicates the relative improvement of 36% for NRMSE and 99% in terms of NMBE.

Likewise, due to the same reasons discussed for DTU FT, the DBPG2 model is able to bring higher accuracy than PVlib for DTU SAT case. According to Fig. 5a and b, NRMSE values are 0.97% for PVlib and 0.61% for the DBPG2 model, while the corresponding values of NMBE are 0.35% and 0.13%, respectively. The enhancement in both NRMSE and NMBE is significant for this case, as well. For NRMSE, 37% and for NMBE, 63% reduction have been achieved.

In the Turku VER case, the modules were installed on a flat rooftop covered with dark concrete roof tiles. During some parts of the year, this surface is covered by snow, while for the rest of the year, the dark tiles remain exposed. As a result, even for similar values of $\cos(AOI)$ and K_{CS} , the irradiance received on the rear side of the modules can vary notably (As one example, the ground coverage for a specific time of the two subsequent days in the winter with the same irradiance level could be different). The estimation of the DBPG2 model, however, tends to represent an average for such conditions, which can result in noticeable deviations from the actual values. This leads to the increase in error of the DBPG2 model. On the other hand, PVlib is able to capture these variations more accurately since it uses the measured RTI directly as an input. In addition, in this case, the string has only 4 modules. It means the edge effect is not considerable and the measured RTI could properly represent the whole string. Therefore, although NMBE is slightly lower for the DBPG2 model, the overall performance is better for PVlib, as reflected by its lower NRMSE in this case. PVlib provides an NRMSE of 1.60% and an NMBE of 0.15% (Fig. 4c). For the DBPG2 model, the values are 2.47% and 0.03%, respectively (Fig. 4d). In a nutshell, it should be noted that we could not avoid RTI measurement for a vertical case. Therefore, there will not be the necessity for modelling a vertical BFPV in the condition without RTI in reality and as an exercise, the DBPG2 model is developed here to compare the results with the other configurations.

Table 3
Characteristics of the training data for SAT cases.

Parameter	Unit	Description	DTU SAT	NREL BEST SAT	EURAC SAT Black Ground	EURAC SAT White Ground
Number of training data	–	Value	190	6432	1917	16245
Temporal coverage	–	Start	Feb 2020	Dec 2019	Jul 2022	Oct 2022
		End	Mar 2020	Dec 2020	Oct 2022	Nov 2024
Variation range of cos (AOI)	–	Min	0.0754	0.4463	0.5732	0.3016
		Max	0.9994	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Variation range of K_{CS}	–	Min	0.0523	0.0117	0.0145	0.0129
		Max	1.4000	1.4000	1.3023	1.4000
Variation range of AZ	deg	Min	90.8	64.5	78.8	60.4
		Max	274.4	296.2	290.9	301.3
Variation range of EL	deg	Min	5.0	5.0	6.6	5.0
		Max	38.3	73.7	66.7	67.0
Variation range of DBPG	–	Min	4.4118e-04	1.1081e-05	1.5108e-05	6.3491e-07
		Max	0.0526	0.1847	0.0649	0.1795

Table 4
The coefficients of polynomial to determine DBPG by Eq. (13), which is for FT cases.

Coefficient	Unit	DTU FT	Turku VER (Sun on the front)	Turku VER (Sun on the back)
a_0	–	–0.0084	–0.0099	–0.0166
a_1	–	0.0224	0.1152	0.1515
a_2	–	0.0494	0.1019	0.1469
a_{12}	–	0.0030	–0.0356	–0.0703
a_{11}	–	0	–0.0998	–0.1266
a_{22}	–	–0.0294	–0.0299	–0.0444

Table 5
The coefficients of polynomial to determine DBPG by Eq. (14), which is for SAT cases.

Coefficient	Unit	DTU SAT	NREL BEST SAT	EURAC SAT Black Ground	EURAC SAT White Ground
a_0	–	0.0081	0.0738	0.0124	–0.1350
a_1	–	0.0095	–0.1559	–0.2335	0.1618
a_2	–	0.0058	0.0241	–0.0070	0.0875
a_3	1/deg	–0.0001	–0.0004	0.0004	0.0006
a_4	1/deg	0.0009	0.0028	0.0016	0.0013
a_{12}	–	–0.0055	–0.0318	0.0392	–0.0187
a_{13}	1/deg	6.276e-05	0.0007	–0.0006	–0.0002
a_{14}	1/deg	1.852e-05	–0.0029	–0.0028	–0.0026
a_{23}	1/deg	0.0003	3.116e-05	8.561e-05	–0.0002
a_{24}	1/deg	–1.511e-06	0.0002	0.0002	0.0015
a_{34}	(1/deg) ²	0	0	1.305e-06	–1.162e-06
a_{11}	–	–0.0132	0.0717	0.2670	–0.0265
a_{22}	–	–0.0052	0	0.0037	–0.0281
a_{33}	(1/deg) ²	3.592e-07	–8.000e-07	2.627e-07	–9.139e-07
a_{44}	(1/deg) ²	–2.200e-06	–2.960e-06	1.213e-05	1.932e-05

There is also a snow period at the NREL BEST SAT site; however, it is typically limited to February. The period is much shorter than Turku, in which snow on the surface might be seen from late September to late March. In addition, at the NREL BEST SAT location, snow usually falls during a short time window and then melts. It does not follow the same pattern as in Turku, where snow may fall, melt, and then fall again, creating several not continues snow-covered periods. In other times of the year, at the NREL BEST SAT site, the ground is covered by grass, with slight seasonal changes in the color, and consequently, the albedo. Therefore, the phenomenon that caused a considerable increase in the error of the DBPG2 model in Turku VER is not dominant here. Another issue is the input variables of the DBPG2 model include AZ and EL for NREL BEST SAT in contrast to Turku VER, which could partially describe

the seasonal changes in the ground cover material. On the other hand, despite Turku VER, the edge effect is considerable here due to the string size. Therefore, the DBPG2 model is able to offer higher accuracy compared to PVlib for NREL BEST SAT. Based on the values reported in Fig. 5c and d, the DBPG2 model provides a 38% improvement in NRMSE compared to PVlib. PVlib shows an NRMSE of 3.01% (Fig. 5c), while the corresponding value for the DBPG2 model is 1.88% (Fig. 5d). Regarding bias, the NMBE for PVlib is 2.27% (Fig. 5c), whereas it is only 0.04% for the DBPG2 model (Fig. 5d), representing a 98% reduction.

For both white and black ground conditions of the EURAC SAT BFPV system, the DBPG2 model is able to estimate power with better accuracy than PVlib. When ground is black, NRMSE and NMBE for PVlib are 2.07% and 1.62% (Fig. 5e). Using the DBPG2 model leads to significant improvement in both error related criteria, where the values of 0.77% and 0.002% are obtained, respectively (Fig. 5f). The results show a relative decrease of 63% in NRMSE and 99% in NMBE.

The edge effect for the white ground condition is more significant than the black ground. Consequently, the DBPG2 model is able to provide higher improvement compared to PVlib for the white ground than the black one. According to Fig. 5g, PVlib offers NRMSE and NMBE of 3.85% and 3.21%. On the other hand, based on Fig. 5h, the DBPG2 model obtains an NRMSE of 1.44% and an NMBE of 0.03%. This means a NRMSE improvement of 63% and NMBE enhancement of 99%, which are equal to the black ground (Relative reduction values are the same, but the absolute decrease values are more for white ground).

To further investigate the performance of the PVlib and DBPG2 models, their power estimation abilities are evaluated for one representative clear-sky day and one representative overcast day in each case. This assessment is conducted by comparing the estimated values with the observed data. The results are illustrated in Fig. 6 for the sample clear-sky days and in Fig. 7 for the sample overcast days.

The plots confirm the previously discussed observations and demonstrate that the DBPG2 model achieves high accuracy levels under both clear-sky and overcast conditions. In all cases, the estimation error of the DBPG2 model remains lower than that of PVlib. The only exception is the Turku case, where, despite the challenging conditions, the DBPG2 model still delivers a reasonably good performance. The higher error compared to PVlib in this case is attributed to the specific factors mentioned earlier.

There are three main reasons for the outperforming of DBPG2 model compared to PVlib. The first is that this model estimates DBPG directly by the historical data, in which the variation in RTI due to the edge effect is taken into account. However, as discussed, PVlib works with RTI of one point, which leads to increase in the power estimation error. The second is that the DBPG2 model utilizes the historical DBPG, in which the issues like degradation and soiling are captured. Nonetheless, such issues are not considered in PVlib modeling. The third is that PVlib uses the bifaciality coefficient, which, for some modules in the string, may be lower than that stated by the manufacturer. As observed, in all the investigated cases, the DBPG2 model outperformed PVlib in terms of

Fig. 4. Checking the power estimation accuracy of the DBPG2 model compared to PVlib using the test data for FT cases (a and b) DTU FT; (c and d) Turku VER.

accuracy, except for the vertical case as discussed earlier, for which the DBPG1 model should be used, as will be discussed in section 4.5.

4.3. Yield estimation

After comparing the power estimation errors of PVlib and the DBPG2 model, the analysis now shifts toward evaluating their performance in obtaining the total yield for the investigated cases. Eq. (15) gives the definition of the yield:

$$Y(\text{period}) = \frac{\sum_{t \in \text{period}} P(t)}{P_n} \quad (15)$$

In which $P(t)$ is the power production at time t within the investigated time frame of period . P_n is also the nominal power.

The monthly yield profiles obtained from both PVlib and the DBPG2 model are compared against the measured values in Fig. 8. The yield values presented in Fig. 8 were obtained without applying any filtering to the data. The values of total yield, as the summation of monthly ones, are also reported in Table 6. In addition to the condition without filter application, Table 6 contains the total yield values with filter application, providing a more comprehensive comparison.

In the DTU FT case (Fig. 8a), both models show good agreement with the measured data. Due to falling in the near shadow, the observed value is much lower than the estimation in February. For this month, PVlib has a slightly lower error. However, in March, the DBPG2 model clearly outperforms PVlib, reducing the overestimation. The outcome is a better overall accuracy for the DBPG2 model in estimating the total yield. According to Table 6, the DBPG2 model achieves an error of 5.42%, compared to 7.15% for PVlib, corresponding to a relative improvement of 24.1%.

For DTU SAT, a similar behavior to the DTU FT case is observed: PVlib provides slightly higher accuracy in February, which is followed by a much better estimation of the DBPG2 model in March (Fig. 8b). Comparing the values in Table 6 indicates that, in contrast to DTU FT

with overestimation, the DBPG2 model has underestimation in obtaining the total yield for this case. PVlib, on the other hand, has overestimation in this case, which is the same as DTU FT. In addition, about the values, Table 6 reveals that like DTU FT, for DTU SAT, the DBPG2 model offers much more accurate estimation of the total yield, as the summation of all the monthly values. While PVlib shows an error of 1.98% in the total yield estimation, the DBPG2 model reduces it to 1.55%, corresponding to a 21.9% improvement in accuracy.

In the case of Turku VER, the available data covered a relatively long period of 43 months. To ensure clarity in visual representation, this time span was divided into two approximately equal sub-periods. This approach prevents overcrowding on a single graph and facilitates a clearer observation of the variations over time. The first sub-period, from January 2018 to September 2019, is shown in Fig. 8c, while the second, from October 2019 to July 2021, is presented in Fig. 8d. Fig. 8c and d indicate that the error of the DBPG2 model increases significantly during the months from September to February. As discussed in explanation of the scatter plots, within this period, snow falls in some periods and rooftop cover varies significantly, which leads to considerable DBPG variation during the time and reduction in accuracy of the DBPG2 model. In contrast, PVlib exhibits considerably lower error in this period. However, due to shorter length of days and lower received solar radiation, the yield values for these months are lower than the other months.

As illustrated in Fig. 8c and d, for the majority of the months outside the September–February window (20 months out of 33), the DBPG2 model generally outperforms PVlib in the yield estimation. For the remaining months (13 months out of 33), the estimation errors of the DBPG2 model and PVlib are relatively close and competitive, with PVlib superiority. Combination of all the observed issues for different months is the total yield estimated by both models becomes very similar. Specifically, the total error amounts to 4.05% for PVlib and 4.18% for the DBPG2 model, indicating a 3.2% better performance by PVlib (Table 6). In addition, Fig. 8c and d demonstrate that throughout almost all months, including September to February, both approaches tend to

Fig. 5. Checking the power estimation accuracy of the DBPG2 model compared to PVlib using the test data for SAT cases (a and b) DTU SAT; (c and d) NREL BEST SAT; (e and f) EURAC SAT Black Ground; (g and h) EURAC SAT White Ground.

overestimate the actual values.

Fig. 8e presents the monthly estimated yield values obtained using both PVlib and the DBPG2 model for NREL BEST SAT. The PVlib model consistently shows overestimation across all months except November. Similarly, the DBPG2 model also tends to overestimate yield in most months, with the exception of February and November. In November,

both models exhibit underestimation, and the deviations from the actual values are relatively large, which may stem from a potential bias in the data measurement.

In November, yield is estimated more accurately by PVlib. Nevertheless, for all other months, the DBPG2 model demonstrates superior accuracy in obtaining the yield. As a result, it also achieves a much more

Fig. 6. Hourly profiles of the normalized power to compare PVlib and the DBPG2 model estimation with observation for a sample clear-sky day in each case; (a) DTU FT; (b) DTU SAT; (c) Turku VER; (d) NREL BEST SAT; (e) EURAC SAT Black Ground; (f) EURAC SAT White Ground.

precise estimation of the total yield compared to PVlib. Table 6 shows that the total yield estimation error for PVlib is 6.49%. This value is significantly reduced to 1.64% when using the DBPG2 model, corresponding to a notable 74.7% improvement in accuracy.

Fig. 8f and g illustrate the observed data, as well as estimated values of the monthly yield for the EURAC SAT Black Ground and White Ground conditions, respectively. In both cases, near shadow occurs throughout the year. While this does not affect the measured GTI and RTI, it reduces the actual power output, leading to seeing overestimation of the monthly yield for PVlib. The DBPG2 model has been also trained using the filtered (near shadow excluded) data. Therefore, it has also overestimation for the period with shadow, and consequently, the whole of a month.

The DBPG2 model is found to have a better performance than PVlib across all months of the investigated period for both black and white ground conditions of EURAC SAT plant. In the white ground, with wider time span, notable improvements are seen from October to January due to stronger edge effect and higher contribution of the rear side on the total power production.

Based on Table 6, employing PVlib is accompanied by the error

values of 7.16% and 11.85% in the estimation of the total yield for the black and white ground cases of EURAC SAT plant, respectively. With the DBPG2 model, the errors drop to 4.01% and 3.66%, indicating the substantial improvements of 44.0% and 69.1% compared to PVlib, respectively.

With application of the filter, it is expected both PVlib and the DBPG2 model to perform better. The DBPG2 model has been trained using the filtered data. Therefore, another expectation is that it experiences more improvement in accuracy than PVlib by application of the filter. This leads to the DBPG2 model achieving greater improvement in yield estimation accuracy in all the cases for which it already outperformed PVlib without filter application. Even for Turku VER, with the competitive opposite condition of errors during the seasons with and without snow, the slightly better accuracy of PVlib in total yield estimation without filter application shifts to the moderate superiority of the DBPG2 model when the filter is utilized. According to Table 6, the changes in the difference between DBPG2 model and PVlib total yield estimation accuracies before and after applying the filter are 24.1%–62.5% for DTU FT, 21.9%–55.1% for DTU SAT, –3.2%–25.4% for Turku VER, 74.7%–77.7% for NREL BEST SAT, 44.0%–53.4% for EURAC SAT

Fig. 7. Hourly profiles of the normalized power to compare PVlib and the DBPG2 model estimation with observation for a sample overcast day in each case; (a) DTU FT; (b) DTU SAT; (c) Turku VER; (d) NREL BEST SAT; (e) EURAC SAT Black Ground; (f) EURAC SAT White Ground.

Black Ground, and 69.1%–83.6% for EURAC SAT White Ground.

4.4. Data selection sensitivity

To verify that the accuracy of the model does not depend on the used training and test data selection procedure, and thus to ensure the reliability of the obtained results, we carried out an additional investigation. The investigation aims to examine different methods to select the data for training and test.

4.4.1. Annual selection vs. random selection

Due to lack of data for two years for a number of the investigated cases, in the previous analyses, the default approach for selecting the test data was the random selection, which has been applied to all the investigated cases. In addition to the random selection, if there is available data for two years or more, the training and test data could be picked up by the annual selection. In that condition, there is the possibility of training the DBPG2 model with data for one year, and test with the data of another year. The available data for Turku VER and EURAC SAT White Ground cover more than two years. Therefore, it is feasible to

develop and test the DBPG2 model using the annual selection for them. Table 7 shows the values of the error criteria for these two cases. In this table, the results obtained from the random selection are also provided, enabling a comparison between the random and annual test data selection methods.

The data for EURAC SAT White Ground covers almost 26 months. Therefore, the first 12 months is selected for training and the next 12 months is chosen for test. In Turku VER, the data is available for more than 3 years (43 months). It offers the opportunity to have two two-year periods to be used for model training and testing. In the first selection, data from January to December 2018 is used for training, and data in the same period in 2019 has been employed for test. In the second selection, the model is trained with data from January to December 2019, and tested using data from January to December 2020.

According to Table 7 whether random or annual selection is utilized, the DBPG2 model performs well. In addition, there is no change in the approach with lower error in each case, which is PVlib in Turku VER and the DBPG2 model in EURAC SAT White Ground. However, the annual selection brings higher error in terms of NRMSE and NMBE for both cases.

This increase in error for the annual selection can be attributed to three issues. The first one is higher number of test data in the annual selection compared to the random selection. Therefore, with the annual selection there is the probability to have more points with great deviation from the actual value, which leads to the increase in both NRMSE and NMBE. The second issue is not considering degradation in PVlib.

The test data for random selection has points since beginning to the end. Nonetheless, the test data for the annual selection does not include the initial period. Therefore, neglecting degradation results in higher PVlib error for the annual selection. Another issue is several time-dependent effective factors that do not follow a constant annual cycle. For such factors, the value or condition is not the same from an exact time in one

Fig. 8. (continued).

(e)

(f)

(g)

Fig. 8. Monthly yield profiles obtained by PVlib and the DBPG2 model compared to the observed values; (a) DTU FT; (b) DTU SAT; (c) Turku VER (Part 1); (d) Turku VER (Part 2); (e) NREL BEST SAT; (f) EURAC SAT Black Ground; (g) EURAC SAT White Ground.

year to another one. Ambient temperature is among such parameters, while for example, a year could be very hot in the summer and another is not. When the DBPG2 model is trained using data from a single year, these interannual variations are entirely unaccounted for, as the model only learns patterns from that specific year's conditions. However, in the random selection approach—where training samples are drawn from multiple years—the model is exposed to a broader range of conditions, thereby partially capturing such variations.

The "partial" consideration stems from two key issues.

1. Rare or extreme conditions may exist in the dataset, but their number is too small compared to the overall data, so their effect is not adequately learned during training (e.g., a PV system with only a few days with snow on the ground that substantially increase albedo and RTI). Since such conditions occur rarely, they occupy a very small

Table 6
Evaluation of PVlib and the DBPG2 model in estimation of the total yield^a.

The case	Period	The employed data	Obtained yield ($\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{kW}_p^{\text{BF front}}}$)			Error (%)	
			Measurement	PVlib	DBPG2 model	PVlib	DBPG2 model
DTU FT	~2 months	No filter applied	156.7	167.9	165.2	7.15	<u>5.42</u>
		Statistical filter applied	128.2	131.4	129.4	2.50	<u>0.94</u>
DTU SAT	~2 months	No filter applied	161.6	164.8	159.1	1.98	<u>1.55</u>
		Statistical filter applied	122.7	127.6	120.5	3.99	<u>1.79</u>
Turku VER	~43 months	No filter applied	3572.1	3716.8	3721.4	<u>4.05</u>	4.18
		Statistical filter applied	3050.4	3092.9	3082.1	1.39	<u>1.04</u>
NREL BEST SAT	~13 months	No filter applied	1824.0	1942.3	1853.9	6.49	<u>1.64</u>
		Statistical filter applied	1724.6	1812.0	1744.1	5.07	<u>1.13</u>
EURAC SAT Black Ground	~3 months	No filter applied	578.0	619.4	601.2	7.16	<u>4.01</u>
		Statistical filter applied	569.1	601.5	584.2	5.69	<u>2.65</u>
EURAC SAT White Ground	~26 months	No filter applied	3144.4	3517.0	3259.6	11.85	<u>3.66</u>
		Statistical filter applied	3119.9	3413.1	3167.9	9.40	<u>1.54</u>

^a In each row, the error for the approach with better yield estimation accuracy is made bold and underlined.

portion of the training data, which means the model may never properly learn how to handle them.

- Due to its stochastic nature, random selection cannot guarantee a perfectly balanced distribution of data across years or seasons. In fact, perfect balance is unlikely to be achieved, since the lengths of seasons vary from year to year. As a result, some conditions may be overrepresented while others remain underrepresented, which introduces bias into the model (e.g., suppose the dataset covers three years: one with an exceptionally long hot summer, one with an average summer, and one with a short cool summer. If random selection happens to include more samples from the extremely hot summer and fewer from the cool summer, the model will learn the hot-summer behavior more strongly, while its performance under cooler summer conditions will be less accurate).

4.4.2. Moving window strategy vs. random selection

Developing the DBPG2 model could be also done using the moving window for training and test periods. Here, the length of training window is considered 30 days, while test window covers the 7 subsequent days. The process starts from the first day and continues until the last possible period. In that way, instead of a polynomial with the same coefficient for the whole period, a number of polynomials are obtained. The coefficients for each polynomial is different and it is valid for the corresponding time span. Evaluation is performed on the complete test data set, which is formed by combining all the 7-day test segments obtained from each step of the DBPG2 model development using the moving window approach. The accuracy of PVlib is also measured for the same test data set. Fig. 9a presents the NRMSE values, while Fig. 9b reports the NMBE values.

In addition to the moving window condition, the values for the random selection are also given in Fig. 9a and b for comparison. The test data for the random selection is different from the moving window and they contain 30% of the data. It means smaller statistical population of test data for random selection compared to the moving window. This difference leads to higher error levels of both PVlib and DBPG2 models for moving window approach, as discussed in the annual selection results.

According to Fig. 9a and b, switching from the random selection to the moving window approach does not change the best-performing model in any of the cases. This is similar to what was observed for the annual selection strategy results.

More discussion could be done using the variation profile of NRMSE for the 7-day test windows. For this purpose, three cases are selected. The first one is EURAC SAT White Ground, with not changing in the ground coverage material. The second one is NREL BEST SAT, with moderate changes in the ground coverage material in some parts of the year. The third one is also Turku VER, with significant changes in the

coming reflected irradiance due to variation of ground coverage. The results are illustrated in Fig. 10a–c, respectively. Although the profiles in Fig. 10a are continuous, discontinuities are seen in Fig. 10b and c. The reason for the observed discontinuities is having some periods for NREL BEST and Turku VER without the available data (e.g., due to sensor failure or maintenance). There must be data for both training and test in each stage of the model development by the moving window strategy. Non-availability of data for either training or test purposes in an investigated time interval leads to exclusion of the corresponding test window, meaning no error value (e.g., NRMSE) is generated for that period. This results in visible breaks in the plotted time series.

Fig. 10a indicates that for all the test windows, the DBPG2 model outperforms PVlib in the EURAC SAT White Ground case. Both models exhibit fluctuations in their NRMSE values. The DBPG2 model is more stable in terms of variation in NRMSE, while PVlib shows a larger variation range. The windows in which PVlib has high error values are seen in several seasons. This could come from various factors, including not considering the edge effect in the seasons it is more important. Another reason might be overestimation or underestimation of the characteristics such as the bifaciality factor or temperature coefficients.

Likewise, for the DBPG2 model, there are some windows with higher error than the neighbors. Considerable variation of the parameters like ambient temperature or wind velocity from the training part to the test segment could be one potential reason. These parameters are not among the input variables of the DBPG2 model, but they can still affect its output. Even if all input variables remain the same, a significant change in such external factors can lead to different DBPG values. Overestimation or underestimation of the characteristics, which is also utilized here for MFPV power production estimation, could be another reason.

Fig. 10b illustrates the variation profile for NREL BEST SAT. From

Table 7
Training and test data selection sensitivity study.

Case	Data selection	Metric	DBPG2 model (%)	PVlib (%)
Turku VER	Random selection	NRMSE	2.47	1.60
	Annual selection (1 st year (Training) and 2 nd year (Test))	NMBE	0.03	0.15
		NRMSE	3.08	2.15
		NMBE	0.60	0.38
Annual selection (2 nd year (Training) and 3 rd year (Test))	NRMSE	3.21	2.25	
	NMBE	0.67	0.75	
EURAC SAT White Ground	Random selection	NRMSE	1.44	3.85
	Annual selection	NMBE	−0.03	3.21
		NRMSE	2.30	4.64
		NMBE	0.99	3.53

January to middle of April, the ground cover at the NREL BEST SAT site undergoes significant changes. This is due to the periods with snow accumulation and melting, followed by the growth of grass. As a result, training and test segments may experience different ground cover conditions in a given step within this period. Such variations can increase the error of the DBPG2 model in certain windows compared to others, as confirmed by Fig. 10b.

After the middle of April, the DBPG2 model clearly outperforms PVlib with a notable margin. Within this time frame, the DBPG2 model error remains relatively stable, except for one jump in the second-to-last window. This increase may be caused by unexpected variations in meteorological parameters that influence the DBPG value during the test period. One example is a sudden rise or drop in the ambient temperature during the test segment compared to the training part.

On the other hand, since PVlib uses RTI as one of its input variables, it shows competitive performance with the DBPG2 model in some parts of the January to mid-April period for NREL BEST SAT. In fact, for certain windows, it even achieves lower error values, as seen in Fig. 10b.

Such windows with better accuracy for PVlib likely correspond to the

situations where the training data covers periods with significant changes in ground cover, while the test data falls within a more stable condition. In such cases, using the measured RTI at a single point—despite not accounting for the edge effect—can lead to better results than the DBPG2 model trained with different ground conditions.

After mid-April and until the end of the period, the error of PVlib remains high due to various reasons, including those discussed for the EURAC SAT White Ground case. In this range, PVlib consistently performs worse than the DBPG2 model, and no window is found where PVlib achieves a lower error—even in the week before the end when the DBPG2 model error increases.

Turku VER is a case with significant changes in the received solar irradiance on the back. For this case, from late September to March, the ground cover varies due to snowfall and melting cycles with no regular time frequency. Therefore, and based on what has been discussed for NREL BEST SAT, during this period, the DBPG2 model shows higher error values compared to PVlib (Fig. 10c).

Fig. 10c also shows that the period with higher error of the DBPG2 model compared to PVlib is not limited to late September to March, and

Fig. 9. Comparing the random selection and moving window approaches in estimation of the power output; (a) NRMSE; (b) NMBE.

it covers the whole year. This is mainly due to the small size of string, which means the edge effect is not significant. Therefore, using the measured RTI in PVlib bring high accuracy.

The DBPG2 model development using the moving window approach offers a major advantage: it can be developed and applied by significantly less data. As a way to improve accuracy, almost similar ground cover periods could be identified—especially in cases where ground conditions vary significantly over the time. Then, moving window approach starts from the beginning. If the variation in the surface conditions within the default window length is not very high, that length is

used. Otherwise, the window length is adjusted based on the identified ground cover category. This means that the DBPG2 model is developed using a smart and adaptive window length selection strategy.

In addition, the proposed moving window approach could be also used as a tool for system performance monitoring. For this purpose, the estimation of the DBPG2 model in each test window can be compared with the measured values. When the error is low, the system is likely performing well. However, when the error becomes high, it may indicate a potential issue in system performance. In fact, it could introduce “the points and periods for more inspection”.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 10. Variation of NRMSE across test segments for the DBPG2 model developed using the moving window approach, compared with the corresponding values obtained from PVlib; (a) EURAC SAT White Ground; (b) NREL BEST SAT; (c) Turku VER.

On the other hand, one limitation of this approach, compared to random selection, is its sensitivity to problems in the training data. If the training window includes a period with measurement problems—like a temporary bias—it can lead to poor model performance for the test segment. In contrast, the random selection method draws data from a broader range, reducing the impact of such localized issues.

4.5. Comparing PVlib, DBPG1 and DBPG2 models

The available recorded RTI data is available throughout the entire investigated time frame for the six investigated cases. Consequently, it is possible to develop the DBPG1 model for them and compare its performance with that of the DBPG2 model and PVlib. The results are given in Fig. 11 in a color-coded table similar to that used in section 4.1. In the provided presentation, the PVlib column is shown in a neutral color (light gray). A coloring scheme was applied for other cells based on these rules.

- If both DBPG models outperform PVlib, the one with the lowest error is highlighted in dark green, while the other is shown in light green.
- If both DBPG models perform worse than PVlib, the one with the highest error is highlighted in dark red, while the other is shown in light red.
- If only one of the DBPG models outperforms PVlib, that model is marked in dark green, and the other model (with worse accuracy than PVlib) is indicated in dark red.

In addition, for each case, the values associated with the DBPG1 and DBPG2 models are shown in bold if their NRMSE is lower than that of PVlib. Additionally, the value corresponding to the model with the lowest NRMSE among all three is underlined.

Fig. 11 indicates that the DBPG1 model delivers superior performance to PVlib in all the cases where it is applicable. It includes Turku VER as the only case where the DBPG2 model does not outperform PVlib. This point in addition to better values of DBPG2 model for other cases than Turku VER, demonstrates the superiority of the both versions of the DBPG model to PVlib in power estimation. In each and every case, there is at least one version of DBPG model with better performance than PVlib.

A comparison between the DBPG1 and DBPG2 models reveals that, in cases where significant temporal variation in ground cover occurs, the DBPG2 model tends to produce higher errors than the DBPG1 model. This is observed in NREL BEST SAT and Turku VER cases, both of which experience notable changes in ground reflectance over time.

In such conditions, the DBPG2 model tends to adopt an averaging approach to minimize the overall error by accounting for all the training data points with input variable vectors that are numerically close in all components. Among several groups of the data points with the aforementioned criterion, one example is the similar hours of clear-sky days at the beginning of November and February. The data points in these two periods share almost the same solar position, AOI, and clearness

index. However, one period might be with snow on the ground, while in another, the surface is covered with a different material, e.g., grass or concrete block. Despite the DBPG2 model attempting to reduce the error through averaging, the resulting deviation from the actual values in such cases leads to higher errors compared to the DBPG1 model, which directly uses the RTI data and is therefore, not affected by this issue.

Increasing the duration and intensity of the ground cover variation results in larger difference between the DBPG1 and DBPG2 model error values. For that reason, a lower difference between errors of DBPG1 and DBPG2 is seen in NREL BEST SAT (An absolute difference of 0.40%). In Turku VER, the DBPG2 model not only performs more significantly worse than DBPG1 (with 0.98% bigger NRMSE), but also shows higher error than PVlib.

On the other hand, when the ground coverage material does not have considerable variation, the DBPG2 model has a better performance than the DBPG1 model. This superiority is primarily because the DBPG2 model can account for the edge effect. In such conditions, there is no major interference from ground albedo variation, which would otherwise cancel out the positive impact of accounting for the edge effect by the DBPG2 model. This behavior is observed in the cases of DTU FT, DTU SAT, EURAC SAT Black Ground, and EURAC SAT White Ground. For these four mentioned cases, the absolute differences of 0.14%, 0.17%, 0.34%, and 0.23% between DBPG2 and DBPG1 models have been seen, respectively.

5. Summary and conclusions

A novel physical data-driven model was proposed to estimate DBPG, and consequently, power output of a BFPV system. The model was called DBPG2 model. The DBPG2 model has been developed for a FT and a SAT system, in Roskilde, Denmark (DTU), a vertically mounted system, in Turku, Finland, one string from NREL BEST SAT plant, in the Colorado, the USA, and a SAT plant, in EURAC Research, Bolzano, Italy. For EURAC plant, model development has been carried out for black ground (low albedo) and white ground (high albedo) conditions. The acronyms DTU FT, DTU SAT, Turku VER, NREL BEST SAT, EURAC SAT Black Ground, and EURAC SAT White Ground were chosen for the cases to have easier indication.

There were severe changes in the ground coverage material for Turku VER with irregular time frequency due to snow falling and melting. For that reason, in addition to the point that the string size was small and the edge effect was not significant, PVlib, as a model that worked with RTI, performed better than the DBPG2 model in this case (1.60% vs. 2.47% for NRMSE). Nonetheless, both models were very close in terms of yield estimation as the majority of power had been produced outside the snow fall season (PVlib had a 3.2% better estimation).

For other cases, the DBPG2 model outperformed PVlib. There were 35.8%, 37.1%, 37.5%, 62.8%, and 62.6% improvement in terms of power estimation NRMSE for DTU FT, DTU SAT, NREL BEST SAT, EURAC SAT Black Ground, and EURAC SAT White Ground cases,

Case	Criterion	The DBPG1 model	The DBPG2 model	PVlib
DTU FT	NRMSE	0.75%	0.61%	0.95%
	NMBE	-0.27%	-0.00%	0.20%
DTU SAT	NRMSE	0.78%	0.61%	0.97%
	NMBE	-0.23%	0.13%	0.35%
Turku VER	NRMSE	1.49%	2.47%	1.60%
	NMBE	-0.03%	0.03%	0.15%
NREL BEST	NRMSE	1.48%	1.88%	3.01%
	NMBE	0.09%	0.04%	2.27%
EURAC SAT Black Ground	NRMSE	1.11%	0.77%	2.07%
	NMBE	-0.08%	0.00%	1.62%
EURAC SAT White Ground	NRMSE	1.67%	1.44%	3.85%
	NMBE	0.18%	-0.03%	3.21%

Fig. 11. Comparison of power estimation accuracy of the DBPG1, DBPG2, and PVlib models for the investigated cases.

respectively. The improvement was greater for SAT compared to FT, and for the cases with lower changes in the ground coverage compared to the ones with higher variation of that. For these five cases, the DBPG2 model could also provide a more accurate yield estimation, as well. It included 24.1%, 21.9%, 74.7%, 44.0%, and 69.1% improvement compared to PVlib for DTU FT, DTU SAT, NREL BEST SAT, EURAC SAT Black Ground, and EURAC SAT White Ground cases, respectively.

Overall, the DBPG2 model was found to provide high accuracy for all the investigated cases. This demonstrates the broad applicability of this model across different BFPV configurations and climatic conditions as its coefficients are derived individually for each case without requiring rear irradiance or albedo as inputs, which makes it suitable for diverse real-world scenarios. Nevertheless, the only limitation identified was in vertical installations with a small number of PV modules and highly variable ground cover (e.g., snow accumulation and melting). Apart from this case, the DBPG2 model outperformed PVlib.

BFPV systems are getting very popular in the agriculture, which is referred as Agri PV. Due to crop growth, the albedo changes much more widely than the power production application. Therefore, as a potential idea for future research works, model development could be done to find data-driven models to obtain RTI or directly DBPG, and consequently, output power of the system in that application. Another idea would be using the historical data to find the impact of different effects and obtain performance loss rate (PLR). PLR could be applied to PVlib to make it both data-driven and more accurate, and it could be compared with original PVlib and also the DBPG models. In addition, the DBPG2 model could be combined with the weather forecasting methods to solve the severe ground coverage changes issue in the cases like Turku VER. Similarly, a parameter describing vegetation could be also included for the cases with grass like NREL BEST SAT. Furthermore, one more promising avenue for future research would be extending the model to a coupled photo-thermal-electrical system by incorporating critical environmental factors such as ambient temperature and wind speed.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ali Sohani: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marco Pierro:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gianluigi Bovesecchi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **David Moser:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Cristina Cornaro:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used ChatGPT and DeepSeek to assist with English language editing. Following the use of this tool, the authors carefully reviewed and revised the content to ensure its accuracy and appropriateness. The authors take full responsibility for the final content of this publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data for EURAC cases are confidential. For others, data will be made available on request.

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